

Factors Affecting on Drop-Out of Students at F.Sc Level: A Case Study

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Ghulam Sughra

PhD Scholar, Department of Education, Mohi-Ud-Din Islamic University Nerian
Sharif AJK

Muhammad Iqbal

PhD Scholar, Department of Education, International Islamic University, Islamabad.

Sufi Amin

Research Fellow, International Islamic University, Islamabad.

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore the drop-out ratio at college level including analysis of socio-economic and institutional factors. The population of the study was all the students and teachers of Islamabad Model Colleges for boys at F.Sc level. The methodology for the study was quantitative in nature. Besides, self-structured questionnaire was used as data collection instruments. Questionnaire was constructed according to five point Likert Scale. The validity and reliability of the instrument was ensured. Further, the reliability of the instrument was checked through Cronbach Alpha. The researcher personally visit all the selected institutes and collect the data. Moreover, Frequency, percentage, mean score and standard deviation was used a statistical tools including SPSS was used as data analysis software. The data after analysis was presented in the form of tables and figures. Major recommendations of the study were: Government must ensure the presence of teachers at schools in school hours. For this purpose involvement of parents and community members is vital. Better conduct of teachers can bring revolution in the field of education. Teacher-student relationship plays a dynamic role in the learning processes of children. It is one of the most essential areas through which teachers can not only attract students to schools but also make the teaching-learning a fun experience for the children. And for the enhancement of professional career and to coup the new challenges need base refresher courses, workshops and seminars should be organized for head teachers and teachers.

Keywords: Drop-Out, Phenomena, Factors, F.Sc Level

Introduction

The cause of a student dropping out is often termed as the antecedent of dropout because it refers to the pivotal event which leads to dropout. This event, however, is the culmination of a much longer process of leaving school that began long before the date that a student actually discontinues attendance. Historic scholarship on school dropout spans from as early as a

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1927 monograph that labeled it “school leaving” and associated those at risk with possible mental inferiority (Butt, 2019). At the same time, previous research has explained dropout causes and even cataloged dropout scholarship from the ensuing decades in terms of content and empirical merit (David, 2017). However, never before have reports of students who dropped out been compared from all the available nationally representative dropout studies and then analyzed. What follows will describe seven nationally representative studies on school dropout and their findings. Also, these studies will be analyzed using the framework of push, pull, and falling out factors, as set forth by Murphy and Meyers (2012), to determine which types of factors were most prominent. The discussion section will posit potential reasons for predominant types of factors, and the implications this has on dropout scholarship in the past, present, and future (Murphy, & Meyers, 2012).

Specifically, individuals with a tertiary level of education have a greater chance of finding a job, a lower unemployment rate, and a higher possibility of having a full time contract and earn more than those who do not have a university degree (UNESCO, 2010). However, as some analysis carried out by the UNESCO have showed, in many countries a substantial number of students enter in the higher education system and leave without at least a first tertiary degree. Even though dropping out does not always represent a failure of individuals or inefficiency of universities, a high dropout rate shows that the higher education system did not probably match the students’ expectations and needs (UNESCO, 2010). In Italy the high dropout rate after the first year (as well as the high number of students who do not pass exams) has been considered, in the last two decades, one of the weaknesses of the higher education system. With the aim of, among others, increasing the participation and reducing the dropout rate in higher education, the Italian university system has been reformed in the last year’s. Even though the number of entrants who do not enroll in the second year has been shrinking. (16.7% in the academic year 2008/2009), the dropout rate at the end of the first year is still very high (UNESCO, 2008).

A study in India researcher found the reasons of students’ school dropouts, In India due to financial problems and expenses dropout rate is high. So students drop out their school to fulfill their financial needs (Hussain, 2011). According to Bangladesh News.Com the year 2005 to 2006, 1.7 million students were enrolled in secondary education level but about 0.7 million students’ dropout without completing their secondary education and higher secondary education examination in 2007. Like other developing countries, Pakistan is facing challenges in improving the quality of education. However, the country has been facing low enrollment and high drop out of students at primary level which is directly related with the literacy rate in the country (Malik, 2012).

Education is a vital prerequisite for combating poverty, empowering women, protecting children from hazardous and exploitative labor, promoting human rights, protecting the environment, and influencing population growth. Hence the level of education is a key indicator for devolution planning. The UNDP Millennium Development Goals report states that Pakistan will not be able to achieve its education goals until 2015. Approximately 50% of enrolled children drop out before completing primary education. In 1977 study shown that 79% of dropouts are from low-income families (Staff writer, 2007). Overall in Pakistan students’ dropouts’ rate is 50% for both girls and boys (Khan, Azhar & Shah, 2011, p.1). Students drop outs rate for girls was 30 % and 27 % for boys in South Africa, and that

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rate was examined for students, who dropped out due to school dues before their matriculation (Smink & Schargel, 2014). So, the numerical belong to provinces about the education and drop out are more distrusting (Smink, & Schargel, 2014).

Pakistan has the highest proportion of out-of-school children (OOSC) in South Asia. According to UNESCO, over 5.4 million primary-school-age children and 6.9 million lower-secondary-school-age children were out of school in Pakistan in 2011 (UIS, 2012). The Pakistan Education Task Force reported in 2011 that roughly one in 10 of the world's primary-school-age children who are not in school live in Pakistan, thereby placing Pakistan second in the global ranking of OOSC; it is estimated that, of these children, about three million will never enter school. The UNDP Millennium Development Goals report states that Pakistan will not be able to achieve its education goals until 2015. Approximately 50% of enrolled children drop out before completing primary education. In 1977 study shown that 79% of dropouts are from low-income families (Staff writer, 2007). According to the Society for the Protection of the Rights of the Child (SPARC) Islamabad, a local (NGO) advocating the rights of children, 35,000 high school pupils in Pakistan dropout of the education system each year due to corporal punishment. In South Asian countries Pakistan ranked on top of list, where only 10% of population terminating their 12 years of schooling (Farooq, 2008).

In Pakistan only 2% of budget is dedicated to education sector. This situation is not satisfactory for education system of a country. "Dropouts have many implications and remains a common term, but the use of describing the failure in the schools and their students" (Ajaja, 2012). Studies suggest that there is need for research in the area of student dropout that how does it affects the economic conditions of a country. Researchers also argue on conducting a study on comparative analysis of dropout rate in different countries. Researchers argue on conducting research on a larger scale to find out the causes of dropout and their effect on economic conditions (Hertzog, & Morgan, 2014). Findings of previous research shows that there are many socio-economic factors such as high cost of institutes, parents are not interested to educate their children instead they want their children to work and earn, early marriage, security problems that caused the drop out of students from polytechnic institutes (Elliott, Huizinga, & Ageton, 2012).

Purpose of the Study

The ratio of dropout students at college level is a matter of concerns which is prevailing. Keeping in view the issue, analysis leads an examination to investigate reasons and ramifications of the dropout phenomenon at college level. There is a need to find out the research on drop out, so the problem to be investigate the causes of drop out phenomena at FSc level.

Methodology of the Study

It was quantitative study. The nature of the study was descriptive and survey type. Parents, teachers, students, and administrators of all Federal Colleges of Islamabad was the population of the study. The sample of the study was 63 teachers, 123 students, and 14 administrators. Besides, random sampling technique was used. It was a survey type study. The researcher was used three Self-structured questionnaire. These questionnaires were consist close ended questions as well as having five point Likert scale. Validity of the tool was

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insured through experts of the field. The tool was changed according to their suggestions. While reliability of the tool was checked through Cronbach Alpha. It value was .085. Data were analyzed with the help of SPSS (Version, 22) software. Frequency, Percentage, mean score, and Standard Deviation was used as a statistical tools.

Results

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution regarding Factors affecting Dropout

Statement	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strict discipline and regulations causes students' dropout	SA	2	14.3
	A	10	71.4
	U	1	7.1
	DA	1	7.1
	SDA	0	0.0
The college has lack of proper Basic physical and educational facilities	SA	3	21.4
	A	7	50.0
	U	1	7.1
	DA	3	21.4
	SDA	0	0.0
Collecting too much money from the students contribute students' dropout	SA	3	21.4
	A	8	57.1
	U	1	7.1
	DA	2	14.3
	SDA	0	0.0
Lack of choices in programmes, courses etc. is a contributory factor of students' dropout	SA	3	21.4
	A	7	50.0
	U	1	7.1
	DA	1	7.1
	SDA	2	14.3
Ineffective curriculum compels a student to leave his studies before completion	SA	10	71.4
	A	1	7.1
	U	2	14.3
	DA	1	7.1
	SDA	0	0.0
Students' dropout is caused by unfavorable school environment	SA	9	64.3
	A	3	21.4
	U	2	14.3
	DA	0	0.0
	SDA	0	0.0
Teachers' discriminative and autocratic attitudes compel a student to leave college	SA	10	71.4
	A	3	21.4
	U	1	7.1

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	DA	0	0.0
	SDA	0	0.0
Students' dropout is caused by severe corporal punishment	SA	7	50.0
	A	3	21.4
	U	1	7.1
	DA	2	14.3
	SDA	1	7.1
Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout	SA	4	28.6
	A	4	28.6
	U	3	21.4
	DA	3	21.4
	SDA	0	0.0
Lack of students' understanding of subjects taught contribute to students' dropout	SA	9	64.3
	A	2	14.3
	U	2	14.3
	DA	1	7.1
	SDA	0	0.0
Students' dropout is caused by the students' company with unwanted children	SA	4	28.6
	A	7	50.0
	U	2	14.3
	DA	1	7.1
	SDA	0	0.0
Get married/plan to marry in early age contribute to students' dropout	SA	6	42.9
	A	6	42.9
	U	1	7.1
	DA	0	0.0
	SDA	1	7.1
Use illegal drugs during college contribute to students' dropout	SA	3	21.4
	A	5	35.7
	U	3	21.4
	DA	2	14.3
	SDA	1	7.1
Students' dropout is caused by students' poor attendance	SA	2	14.3
	A	8	57.1
	U	1	7.1
	DA	2	14.3
	SDA	1	7.1
Students' disruptive behavior contribute students' dropout	SA	3	21.4
	A	6	42.9
	U	1	7.1
	DA	2	14.3
	SDA	2	14.3

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According to table 1 states that 86% agreed with the statement that strict discipline and regulations causes students' dropout. 7% given no response while 7% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that strict discipline and regulations causes students' dropout. 71% agreed with the statement The College has lack of proper Basic physical and educational facilities 7% given no response while 21% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that The College has lack of proper Basic physical and educational facilities. 78% agreed with the statement that collecting too much money from the students contribute students' dropout, 7% given no response, while 14% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that collecting too much money from the students contribute students' dropout. 71% agreed with the statement that Lack of choices in programmes, courses etc. is a contributory factor of students' dropout, 7% given no response, while 21% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Lack of choices in programmes, courses etc. is a contributory factor of students' dropout. 78% agreed with the statement Ineffective curriculum compels a student to leave his studies before completion, 14% given no response, while 7% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Ineffective curriculum compels a student to leave his studies before completion. 83% agreed with the statement that Students' dropout is caused by unfavorable school environment, 14% given no response, while 0% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Students' dropout is caused by unfavourable school environment. 92% agreed with the statement that Teachers' discriminative and autocratic attitudes compel a student to leave college, 8% given no response, while 0% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Teachers' discriminative and autocratic attitudes compel a student to leave college. 71% agreed with the statement that Students' dropout is caused by severe corporal punishment, 7% given no response, while 21% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Students' dropout is caused by severe corporal punishment. 58% agreed with the statement that Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout, 21% given no response, while 21% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout. 78% agreed with the statement that Lack of students' understanding of subjects taught contribute to students' dropout, 14% given no response, while 7% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Lack of students' understanding of subjects taught contribute to students' dropout. 79% agreed with the statement that Students' dropout is caused by the students' company with unwanted children, 7% given no response, while 14% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Students' dropout is caused by the students' company with unwanted children. 86% agreed with the statement that get married/plan to marry in early age contribute to students' dropout, 7% given no response, while 7% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Get married/plan to marry in early age contribute to students' dropout. 57% agreed with the statement that Use illegal drugs during college contribute to students' dropout, 21% given no response, while 22% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Use illegal drugs during college contribute to students' dropout. 71% agreed with the statement that Students' dropout is caused by students' poor attendance, 7% given no

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response, while 21% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Students' dropout is caused by students' poor attendance. And 64% agreed with the statement that Students' disruptive behavior contribute students' dropout, 7% given no response, while 28% disagreed. Thus, it is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that Students' disruptive behavior contribute students' dropout.

Table 2 Mean and SD regarding Factors affecting Dropout

Statement	N	Mean	SD
Strict discipline and regulations causes students' dropout	14	2.21	1.051
The college has lack of proper Basic physical and educational facilities	14	2.29	1.069
Collecting too much money from the students contribute students' dropout	14	2.14	.949
Lack of choices in programmes, courses etc. is a contributory factor of students' dropout	14	2.43	1.342
Ineffective curriculum compels a student to leave his studies before completion	14	1.64	1.216
Students' dropout is caused by unfavorable school environment	14	1.50	.760
Teachers' discriminative and autocratic attitudes compel a student to leave college	14	1.36	.633
Students' dropout is caused by severe corporal punishment	14	2.07	1.385
Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout	14	2.57	1.505
Lack of students' understanding of subjects taught contribute to students' dropout	14	1.71	1.204
Students' dropout is caused by the students' company with unwanted children	14	2.07	1.072
Get married/plan to marry in early age contribute to students' dropout	14	1.86	1.099
Use illegal drugs during college contribute to students' dropout	14	2.50	1.225
Students' dropout is caused by students' poor attendance	14	2.4286	1.15787
Students' disruptive behavior contribute students' dropout	14	2.5714	1.39859

Table 2 directs mean score and standard deviation. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.21, S.D= 1.05) regarding Strict discipline and regulations causes students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.29, S.D= 1.06) regarding the college has lack of proper Basic physical and educational facilities. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.14, S.D= .94) regarding collecting too much money from the students contribute students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.43, S.D= 1.34) regarding Lack of

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choices in programmes, courses etc. is a contributory factor of students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 1.64, S.D= 1.21) regarding Ineffective curriculum compels a student to leave his studies before completion. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 1.50, S.D= .76) regarding Students' dropout is caused by unfavourable school environment. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 1.36, S.D= .63) regarding Teachers' discriminative and autocratic attitudes compel a student to leave college. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.07, S.D= 1.38) regarding Students' dropout is caused by severe corporal punishment. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.57, S.D= 1.50) regarding Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 1.71, S.D= 1.20) regarding Lack of students' understanding of subjects taught contribute to students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.07, S.D= 1.07) regarding Students' dropout is caused by the students' company with unwanted children. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 1.86, S.D= 1.09) regarding Get married/plan to marry in early age contribute to students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.50, S.D= 1.22) regarding Use illegal drugs during college contribute to students' dropout. The mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.42, S.D= 1.15) regarding Students' dropout is caused by students' poor attendance. And the mean score and standard deviation (M= 2.57, S.D= 1.39) regarding Students' disruptive behavior contribute students' dropout.

Conclusions

It is concluded that most of the respondents agreed that strict discipline and regulations causes students' dropout, the College has lack of proper Basic physical and educational facilities, collecting too much money from the students contribute students' dropout, Lack of choices in programmes, courses etc. is a contributory factor of students' dropout, Ineffective curriculum compels a student to leave his studies before completion, Students' dropout is caused by unfavorable school environment, Teachers' discriminative and autocratic attitudes compel a student to leave college, Students' dropout is caused by severe corporal punishment, Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout, Teachers' incompetency also causes students' dropout, Lack of students' understanding of subjects taught contribute to students' dropout, Students' dropout is caused by the students' company with unwanted children, Get married/plan to marry in early age contribute to students' dropout, Use illegal drugs during college contribute to students' dropout, Students' dropout is caused by students' poor attendance. And most of the respondents agreed that Students' disruptive behavior contribute students' dropout.

Recommendations

1. Government must ensure the presence of teachers at schools in school hours. For this purpose involvement of parents and community members is vital.
2. Better conduct of teachers can bring revolution in the field of education. Teacher-student relationship plays a dynamic role in the learning processes of children. It is one of the most essential areas through which teachers can not only attract students to schools but also make the teaching-learning a fun experience for the children.
3. For the enhancement of professional career and to coup the new challenges need base refresher courses, workshops and seminars should be organized for head teachers and teachers.

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